

Emerging adults were identified on the basis of wing markings.

Two species were found: *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and *Marasmia patnalis*. *C. medinalis* accounted for 53% and *M. patnalis* for 47% of the population (see table). *M. patnalis* predominated in Walajah, Thiruvannamalai, and Arakonam divisions; *C. medinalis* in the other divisions. □

Persistence of quinalphos in rice

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We studied the persistence of quinalphos in rice variety Lalat following foliar spraying during 1984-85 kharif and rabi. Quinalphos was sprayed at 0.5 kg ai/ha and 1.0 kg ai/ha, with 3 replications. Plant samples were extracted by chloroform, cleaned by celite:MgO:charcoal column, and

Table 1. Quinalphos residue in rice, 1984-85 dry season (rabi), Bhubaneswar, India.

Days after treatment	Quinalphos residue ^a (ppm)	
	0.5 kg ai/ha	1.0 kg ai/ha
0	5.3	9.5
5	2.5	3.1
10	0.5	1.0
15	n.d.	0.25
20	n.d.	n.d.
50% residue level (d)	3	3

^a n.d. = not detectable.

Table 2. Quinalphos residue in rice, 1985 wet season (kharif), Bhubaneswar, India.

Days after treatment	Quinalphos residue (ppm)	
	0.5 kg ai/ha	1.0 kg ai/ha
0	4.23	6.53
5	1.74	2.71
10	0.27	0.69
15	n.d.	0.34
20	n.d.	n.d.
50% residue level (d)	2.5	3.0

estimated by spectrophotometric method. Recoveries from fortified samples were 80-85%

Initial deposits of quinalphos in rice plant samples were reduced to

nondetectable levels within 15-20 d after treatment during the dry season (Table 1) and within 15-20 d after treatment during the wet season (Table 2). □

Insecticides to control rice hispa

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We evaluated eight insecticides against rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) in a duplicated farmer's field trial during kharif 1986. Plot size was 100 m².

Live grub population from 10 hills/plot was recorded before insecticide application and 1 wk after. Adult beetle population and percent leaf damage on all leaves in 10 hills/plot were assessed 2 wk after insecticide application.

Monocrotophos at 0.06% was most effective against hispa grubs, closely followed by quinalphos at 0.07%. Adult beetle population also was checked by monocrotophos followed by quinalphos (see table). □

Chemical control of rice hispa in Warangal district, Andhra Pradesh, India.^a

Treatment	Grubs/hill		% reduction of grubs	Adults/hill at 14 d after application	% leaf damage
	Before application	7 d after application			
Carbofuran 3G @ 25 kg/ha	12	1 a	87 a	0.4 ab	0.1 ab
Phorate 10G @ 10 kg/ha	9	3 a	60 ab	1.2 b	0.9 ab
Monocrotophos 40EC @ 0.06%	11	1 a	94 a	0.2 a	0.3 ab
Chlorpyrifos 20EC @ 0.06%	7	2 a	69 ab	0.6 ab	0.0 a
Endosulfan 35EC @ 0.09%	12	6 b	42 b	6.8 d	8.0 c
Fenvalerate 20EC @ 0.01%	10	2 a	83 ab	2.5 c	1.8 b
Phosalone 35EC @ 0.09%	10	1 a	89 a	0.8 ab	0.4 ab
Quinalphos 25EC @ 0.07%	10	1 a	92 a	0.3 ab	0.1 ab
Untreated control	10	11 c	-8 c	7.0 d	8.4 c
F test	ns	**	**	**	**
CD (0.05)	-	2	(26)	1.0	(5.70)

^a In a column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

Egg parasites of *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in Sri Lanka

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We studied the yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in Mar and Jul 1982 at the Dryzone Agricultural Research Station, Maha Illuppallama, Sri Lanka. After transplanting, experimental plots were covered with mesh cages. Two weeks after transplanting, plots were exposed

for YSB oviposition. The experiment was repeated four times in two seasons.

Hatched egg masses were collected on day four, remaining egg masses were collected on day eight and held in glass vials in the laboratory. Number of parasites emerging from each egg mass was recorded. Then, egg masses were soaked in 5% HCl and separated into individual eggs and number of hatched eggs, unenclosed dead larvae, and unemerged parasites recorded. Parasites were sent to the Commonwealth Institute of Entomology for identification.

Telenomus sp. and *Tetrastichus*